

Analyzing Job Satisfaction of Optometrists through Psychological Empowerment: A Moderation Analysis

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Abstract:- This study aims to investigate the impacts of all aspects of employee empowerment on job satisfaction through moderation of person-organization fit in order to offer baseline data for the welfare of optometrists and improvement of the working environment. Optometrists working at any level in Pakistan were surveyed using a standardized structured questionnaire for this study. Responses to a 5-point Likert scale questions about job satisfaction, employee empowerment, and person-organization fit were collected. Advanced statistical tools SPSS & Smart PLS were used to analyze the collected data. The results showed that over half of Pakistani optometrists (51.2%) are unsatisfied with their jobs. Optometrists are usually empowered in their profession and influence the workplace and the work they do. Despite this, it was shown that optometrists have a poor level of job satisfaction. Furthermore, the role of Person Organization Fit as a moderating variable was not established. The control variables demonstrated a significant association between pay packages and job satisfaction. The study's findings suggest that optometrists are not content with their work despite their psychological empowerment because of poor remuneration. The configuration of relationships tested is relatively novel.

Keywords:- Employee empowerment, Person-organization fit, Job Satisfaction, Optometrist, Meaningful work, Competence, Self-Determination.

I. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction is one of the most intricate issues confronted by organizations when it comes to managing employees. Job satisfaction is the motivation of employees and feelings toward the work they do (Spector and P. E 1997). A positive and favorable work environment and motivation lead to job satisfaction (Aziri 2011). Organizations that are successful are always distinguished by the contentment of job satisfaction of their employees. Expectation theory states that goal attainment, realization, accomplishment, and well-being are used to measure job satisfaction. Robbins and Stephens (2007) argue that job satisfaction should be broadly construed in order for the notion to interact with an organization's policies and standards to meet the rise in work activities in line with the ideal working environment. This indicates that determining job satisfaction is crucial to carrying out work tasks that coincide with the organization's goals. Job dissatisfaction may lead to staff turnover, absences, poor quality of services, and poor job performance (Marinucci et al. 2013). For many years,

healthcare professional's satisfaction and retention had a basic influence on the provision of basic healthcare services by any organization globally (Akuffo et al. 2021). Several studies show that there are many determinants influencing job satisfaction among healthcare professionals (Zhang et al. 2016). They include opportunities for personal and professional growth, competitive pay, recognition, flexible schedule, good connections with coworkers, and a sense of legitimate achievement from their work, obvious progress of patients, reasonable workload, autonomy on the job, a pleasant working environment, supervision, career advancement, job security, and contingent rewards (Pillay 2009; Zontek et al. 2009). In Pakistan, inadequate working conditions, including little financial incentive, unavailability of resources, unsatisfactory environment, and limited prospects for career advancement lead to poor job satisfaction among healthcare professionals, especially optometrists, and consequently lead to poor quality of services and increased turnover.

Optometry is a rapidly growing field in Pakistan. These eye care professionals seem to work on all platforms, from the Public sector to the private sector, from working in communities to optical shops, majorly contributing to providing essential vision-related services such as refraction and management of diseases (Boadi-Kusi et al. 2015) and some specialized services like managing strabismus, contact lens fitting (Illahi and Cardall 2018) and low vision rehabilitation (Hooper et al. 2008). They also have a significant role in achieving VISION 2020 (eliminating avoidable blindness) (Palmer et al. 2014). Due to their significant role in the community, their job satisfaction is of utmost importance for the provision of quality services. Low job satisfaction among optometrists is causing a career shift. Their turnover intentions are raising certain questions regarding their job satisfaction level. Their empowerment at workplace and relation with their respective organization are in question.

Previous studies show that job satisfaction is affected by employee empowerment. Employee empowerment is the motivational notion of self-efficacy (Conger and Kanungo 1988). Psychological empowerment is defined as a motivational paradigm expressed in four cognitions; competence, meaning, self-determination, and impact. These four cognitions demonstrate an active attitude to a work position in which a person chooses to engage and is capable of influencing their work surroundings (Thomas and Velthouse 1990). Employee empowerment leads to enhanced organizational commitment and increased job involvement (Karia et al. 2006). Person organization fit has an impact on job

satisfaction. Previous literature has shown that employees who are not properly complemented with organization have little job performance. Person organization fit can be a rational interpreter of job performance because people with high person-job fit have found to be more satisfied with their job and have positive work outcome (Edwards and J. R 1991). There is sufficient evidence from prior studies to support the correlations between the two variables i.e. employee empowerment and job satisfaction (Abou Elnaga and Imran 2014) and Person-organization fit and job satisfaction (Chen et al. 2016). To clarify the relationships between all of these variables, though, further research is required. In this study, we will use person- organization as moderator between Employee empowerment and Job satisfaction. Although some studies have been done to assess the job satisfaction level among other Health care workers (Salam 2016). Despite optometrists playing an important part in Pakistan's eye care industry, no study has been done to determine their level of job satisfaction or to give evidence for policy guidance in addressing the country's expanding demand for optometrists. As stated by

World Health Organization's "Global Strategy on Human Resources for Health: Workforce 2030", the strategy agenda is "to ensure a workforce that is suitable for purpose to accomplish the targets of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)". This agenda takes into account the emerging evidence suggesting that resolving the employment issues encountered by healthcare professionals and making investments in the health workforce, particularly optometrists, might enhance socioeconomic development and sustainable economic growth. Low determination among the optometrists of Pakistan may destabilize the excellence of specialized eye care services. This study therefore is an attempt to assess the level of job satisfaction among optometrists of Pakistan and its associated factors. By examining the impact of employee empowerment on professional job satisfaction, this study intended to offer baseline data for the welfare of optometrists and the improvement of their working environment. This study will offer primary data for the first time to aid in facilitating the development of human resource policies for the management of healthcare and optometry practices in Pakistan.

II. RESEARCH MODEL

Employee Empowerment

Fig. 1: Research model depicting the influence of Employee Empowerment on Job Satisfaction under moderating role of Person-Organization fit.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this research study the quantitative research methodology was applied by conducting a cross sectional study in Dec 2022 to assess the factors affecting Job satisfaction among optometrists in Pakistan. The convenience sampling approach, a non-probability sampling technique, was employed. This study used a well-structured questionnaire to collect data from optometrists, employed in Pakistan. After informed consent and ensuring confidentiality, data was collected through a structured questionnaire, completed by participants through online Google forms. Participants having a

Bachelor's degree in Optometry and working in a reputable organization were contacted to participate in the study. The duly completed response was received from 150 Optometrists working in government, private, and NGOs across the country.

IV. MEASURING INSTRUMENT

Data was collected through a structured Questionnaire using three tools i.e. Employee Empowerment, PO- Fit and Job satisfaction. Supplementary information on respondents' socio demographics and job related data was taken. The Employee Empowerment was being measured by adopted and adapted

questionnaire of Spreitzer (1995). It consists of 4 dimensions containing meaningful work, competence, self-determination and impact over work. A 5-point Likert scale was used to rate the responses, ranging from “strongly disagree” (Score: 1) to “strongly agree” (Score 5). Meaningful work has been measured using a three-item scale based on the studies by Spreitzer (1995). The sample item is ‘The work I do is meaningful to me’. The Cronbach’s alpha of the instrument is 0.818. Competence measured by 3 items scale having Cronbach’s alpha of the instrument is 0.784. The sample item is “I have mastered the skills necessary for my job”. Self-determination taken by the study of Spreitzer (1995) had 3 items. The sample item is “I can decide myself how to go about doing my work”. The Cronbach’s alpha of the instrument is 0.768. Impact over work containing three items has internal reliability consistency of 0.854. The sample item is “I have a great deal of control over what happens in my department”

The Person-Organization fit has been measured by the adopted questionnaire of Bretz and Judge (1994). It consists of 15 items which are responded on a Likert scale ranging from 1 “not true at all” to 5 “definitely true”. The questions were asked about the organization in which respondents work in, regarding pays, teamwork, values fairness etc. The Cronbach’s alpha of the instrument is 0.92.

The Job satisfaction has been measured by an adopted and adapted measure by Cook et al (1981). It contains of 7 items measured on a Likert scale ranging from “completely satisfied” (Score 1) to “Completely dissatisfied” (score 5). To determine overall job satisfaction, it evaluates how satisfied employees are with their work, management, coworkers, possibilities for advancement, growth, remuneration, and the company. The Cronbach’s alpha of the instrument is 0.89.

V. RESULTS

The demographics data of Optometrists in Table 1 shows that, out of 150 participants, 53 (35.3%) were male and 97 (64.7%) were female. A greater proportion of participants (n=126, 84%) had education up to Bachelors and 16% (n=24) have completed MS/M.Phil. 57.3% of total population were working in the private sector, others in academics and in NGOs/Trusts, and some of them 4.7% in optical setups. 5.3% have secured a government seat showing there is less recognition of Optometrists at national level. Most of them have a pay package of 30k to 60k and experience of less than 2 years. When asked about the reason for choosing optometry 54% responded that they were very interested in the field but when inquired about choosing another career if given a choice only 36% responded negatively. The remaining either wanted to change or was not sure about it. The mean score (\pm SD) for overall job satisfaction of Optometrists was 2.56 ± 0.99 showing they are not satisfied with their job.

Pearson correlation was used to find the association between the variables. The Correlation Analysis in Table 2 discloses the direction of the relationship among variables. It

describes the strong association between employee empowerment and job satisfaction with $p < 0.01$. The table 3 depicts the moderated regression analysis of variables. Pay package and change career if given a choice served as control variables having $R^2 = 21.6\%$. The unit change in the dependent variable was indicated by the β values for the corresponding independent variables and moderator having aggregate $R^2 = 59.9\%$. The dimensions of employee empowerment didn’t show any association with job satisfaction except for impact over work ($\beta = 0.163$, $p < 0.05$) rejecting the first three hypothesis. Person-organization fit generally impacts job satisfaction ($\beta = -0.620$, $p < 0.01$) however its role as moderator between employee empowerment and job satisfaction is not established.

VI. DISCUSSION

Based on Job Characteristic theory this study has persuaded to check the job satisfaction among optometrists of Pakistan and the impact of all dimensions of Employee empowerment on Job satisfaction with P-O Fit as moderator. The mean score for overall perception of job satisfaction of Optometrists was 2.56. The statistics showed that more than half (51.2%) of Pakistan's optometrists are dissatisfied with their jobs. However, the level of Job satisfaction among Optometrists of the UK is 80% and that of Ghana is 74.3% (Akuffo et al. 2021). Mapping the job satisfaction among other health care professionals of Pakistan it is observed that the health workforce is dissatisfied at all levels. A study held in Lahore showed that only 31% of doctors are satisfied with their job (Deeba et al. 2015). Another study regarding job satisfaction among healthcare professionals showed only 18% of participants are satisfied with their jobs (Tasneem et al. 2018). The major reasons behind low satisfaction are pay packages /remuneration, promotion chances, rewards, benefits, etc. (Kumar et al. 2013). Our study found pay packages to be significantly associated with overall job satisfaction. This result is consistent with the previous studies conducted in optometrists of UK, Ghana (Akuffo et al. 2021), and South Africa (Ramson and Naido 2016). In Pakistan, salary is perceived to be low in health care professionals, especially optometrists, which results in low productivity and Job performance. Hence, the a need for stakeholders to adopt policies intended to improving pay packages and reduce job turnover among optometrists (Ramson and Naido 2016).

This study focuses on impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction. The basic approach of empowerment is to build an environment where employees have freedom to express their views and can make decision about their work. Elaborating the four dimensions of employee empowerment i.e. meaning, competence, self-determination and impact over work, our study found no significant impact of any dimension over job satisfaction except for impact over work. Thus, rejecting most of the hypothesis. This finding conflicts with earlier empirical research, which suggested that people who have a sense of purpose in their jobs tend to invest more time and effort in it and hence more satisfied with their jobs (Wrzesniewski 1997). However, the correlation analysis

showed that meaningful work is negatively linked with job satisfaction ($r = -0.313$, $p < 0.01$). The mean score showed that however, Optometrists find their work meaningful they are still not satisfied with their job. The results are controversial with the findings of Bowie (1998), who stated that meaningful work activities generate interest in a job and greater job satisfaction.

The regression analysis showed no impact of competence on job satisfaction, however, co-relation analysis was significant $p < 0.05$ having $r = -0.322$. Contrary to our study, some of the previous studies indicated that competence had a significant positive influence on job performance. (Syahrudin et al. 2016; Subari and Riady 2015). Our study supports the work of Setyaningdyah et al. (2013) showing that there was no significant impact of the competency on job satisfaction of Optometrists.

No significant results were found while investigating the impact of self-determination on job satisfaction. This finding is not in line with the Self-determination theory showing a positive association between self-determination and job satisfaction. Our study contradicts the result of previous studies by Deci et al. (1989); Vansteenkiste et al. (2007); and Fernandez et al. (2015) showing that an administrative orientation that promotes self-determination positively affects overall satisfaction in employees and that the effect nurtures as work climate particularly increases remuneration and job security. However, the correlation analysis revealed significant association $p < 0.01$ and $r = -0.362$ showing a strong association of self-determination and job satisfaction. The hypothesis showing impact over work influences job satisfaction was accepted as β value was statistically significant. This study supports the Job Characteristic model anticipating that greater the control and autonomy in work greater will be the job satisfaction (Hackman and Oldham 1976; Griffin 1981). Correlation analysis also showed a significant association ($p < 0.001$ $r = -0.570$) between impact of IOW and Job satisfaction.

The role of moderator between job satisfaction and all dimensions of Psychological empowerment i.e. meaningful work, competence, self-determination and Impact over work is not established. Hence, rejecting the remaining hypothesis. Co-relation analysis and regression analysis showed a significant effect of person organization fit on Job satisfaction but its role as a moderator is not established. The role of P-O fit as moderator between meaningful work and job satisfaction was not tested before. The study by Van Wingerden (2018) argued that when employees experience a P-O fit based on shared values, they perceive their work meaningful, and subsequently be more engaged in their job. There was no prior study depicting the role of P-O Fit as moderator between empowerment and Job satisfaction. However, our study indicates that role of moderator is not established. Based on the study it can be concluded that mismatch of values between a person and organization is not a hindrance in achieving job satisfaction if a person is empowered at his job. Moreover, control variable i.e. pay package showed that job satisfaction is greatly impacted by it. No matter how empowered an employee

is or how perfectly he fit with his organization, if he is not getting paid properly, the full job satisfaction can't be achieved.

The results of this study can assist monitoring bodies to improve the productivity and job satisfaction of their employees. It is advised that they implement rules concerning optometric practices and their expanding demands, as well as steps to empower their staff. The research data provides evidence that increasing pay packages leads to greater job satisfaction among Optometrists. They must be acknowledged and empowered at their work to increase their productivity. Findings from this study are crucial for understanding how job satisfaction affects optometrists' productivity and retention at work for employers, policymakers, healthcare managers, and other stakeholders in the eye care industry. Strategic planning and effective management of human resources for eye health in Pakistan are essential in developing quality eye-health systems and providing high-quality eye care services.

Every study comes up with several limitations. Firstly, the data was collected from limited sample; A more representative sample could yield comprehensive information on the issue at hand. Secondly, this study relied on self-report measures liable to self-report bias. The overall response was obtained in a confined environment which leads to provide specific feedback. Furthermore, based on moderate regression analysis indicating unsupported and non-significant result, it is recommended that further research should explore the effect of interaction using other variables in order to achieve significant results. Similarly, adding any mediating variables in this relationship may generate various significant outcomes for future researchers.

VII. CONCLUSION

The results showed that more than half of Pakistan's optometrists (51.2%) are not satisfied with their jobs. Optometrists are usually empowered in their work, as seen by the higher mean scores across all characteristics of employee empowerment; they find their work meaningful and interesting and love what they do. There is greater competency in the field and optometrist are self-determined to do their job efficiently. Additionally, they influence the workplace and the work they do. Despite this, it was shown that optometrists have a poor level of job satisfaction. Furthermore, the role of Person Organization Fit as a moderating variable was not established. Based on the study it can be concluded that a mismatch of values between a person and an organization is not a hindrance in achieving job satisfaction if a person is empowered at his job. The control variables demonstrated a substantial correlation between pay packages and job satisfaction. The study's findings suggest that despite the psychological empowerment, optometrists are not content with their profession because of poor remuneration.

VIII. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The data was collected after taking the Informed consent from the participants. Confidentiality was ensured to them regarding the maintenance of secrecy of their data.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Abou Elnaga, A, and Imran, A. 2014. "The impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction the oretical study." *American Journal of Research Communication*, 2(1): 13-26.
- [2.] Akgunduz, Y., Alkan, C., and Gök, Ö. A. 2018. "Perceived organizational support, employee creativity and proactive personality: the mediating effect of meaning of work." *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 34: 105-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2018.01.004>
- [3.] Akuffo, K. O., Agyei-Manu, E., Kumah, D. B., Danso-Appiah, A., Mohammed, A. S., Asare, A. K., and Addo, E. K. 2021. "Job satisfaction and its associated factors among optometrists in Ghana: a cross-sectional study". *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, 19(1): 1-10.
- [4.] Allen, V.L., and Greenberger, D.B. 1980. "Destruction and perceived control. In A. Baum, J.E. Singer, & J.L. Singer (Eds.)" *Advances in environmental psychology*, 2: 85 – 110.
- [5.] Anuradha, M. V., Srinivas, E. S., Singhal, M., and Ramnarayan, S. 2014. "To work or not to work: Construction of meaning of work and making work choices." *Vikalpa*, 39(2): 7-20.
- [6.] Arthur, W. Jr., Bell, S. T., Villado, A. J., and Doverspike, D. 2006. "The sue of person organization fit in employment decision making: An assessment of its criterion related validity." *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 91: 786-801. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0021-9010.91.4.786>
- [7.] Ashforth, B. E. 1989. "The experience of powerlessness in organizations." *Organizational Behavior and Human Decisian Processes*, 43: 207-242. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(89\)90051-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(89)90051-4)
- [8.] Ashforth, B. E. 1990. "The organizationally induced helplessness syndrome; A preliminary model." *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences*, 7: 30-36. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1936-4490.1990.tb00532.x>
- [9.] Aziri B. 2011 "Job satisfaction: a literature review." *Manag Res Pract*; 3(4).
- [10.] Bandura, A. 1989. "Human agency in social cognitive theory." *American Psychologist*, 44: 1175-1184. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0003-066X.44.9.1175>
- [11.] Bell, N. E., fit Staw, B. M. 1989. "People a.s sculptors versus sculpture. In M. B. Arthur, D. T. Hall. and B. S. Lawrence (Eds.), *Handbaak of career theory*: 232-251.
- [12.] Boadi-Kusi, S. B., Ntodie, M., Mashige, K. P., Owusu-Ansah, A., and Antwi Osei, K. 2015. "A cross-sectional survey of optometrists and optometric practices in Ghana." *Clinical and Experimental Optometry*, 98(5): 473-477. <https://doi.org/10.1111/exo.12291>
- [13.] Boon, C., and Biron, M. 2016. "Temporal issues in person–organization fit, person–job fit and turnover: The role of leader–member exchange." *Human relations*, 69(12): 2177-2200.
- [14.] Bowie, N. E. 1998. "A Kantian theory of meaningful work." *Journal of Business Ethics*, 17(9): 1083-1092
- [15.] Breaguh, J. A. 1985. "The measurement of work autonomy." *Human relations*, 38(6): 551-570. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872678503800604>
- [16.] Bretz, R. D., Jr., and Judge, T. A. 1994. "Person-organization fit and the theory of work adjustment: Implications for satisfaction, tenure, and career success." *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 44: 32-54. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.1994.1003>
- [17.] Brief, A. P., and Nord, W. R. 1990. *Meanings of occupational work*. Lexington, MA: Lexington Books.
- [18.] Brooke, C., and Parker, S. 2009. "Researching spirituality and meaning in the workplace." *The Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 7(1): 1-10.
- [19.] Cable, D. M., and Edwards, J. R. 2004. "Complementary and supplementary fit: A theoretical and empirical integration." *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89: 822-834. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0021-9010.89.5.822>
- [20.] Cable, D.M. and DeRue, D.S. 2002. "The convergent and discriminant validity of subjective fit perceptions." *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(5): 875–884. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0021-9010.87.5.875>
- [21.] Carless, S. A. 2004. "Does psychological empowerment mediate the relationship between psychological climate and job satisfaction?." *Journal of business and psychology*, 18(4): 405-425.
- [22.] Chatman, J.A. 1991. "Matching people and organizations: selection and socialization in public accounting firms." *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 36(3): 459–484. <https://doi.org/10.5465/ambpp.1989.4980837>
- [23.] Chen, P., Sparrow, P., and Cooper, C. 2016. "The relationship between person-organization fit and job satisfaction." *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. 31(5): 946-959. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-08-2014-0236>
- [24.] Chiu, C.-K., Chien, C.-S., Lin, and Hsiao, C.Y. 2005. "Understanding hospital employee job stress and turnover intentions in a practical setting: The moderating role of locus of control." *Journal of Management Development*, 24: 837 – 855.

- [25.] Conger, Jay A., and Rabindra N. Kanungo. 1988 "The empowerment process: Integrating theory and practice." *Academy of management review*, 13(3): 471-482. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1988.4306983>
- [26.] Cook, J. D., Hepworth, S. J., Wall, T. D., and Warr, P. B. 1981. "The experience of work: A compendium of 249 measures and their use." London: Academic Press. p. 26.
- [27.] David, Mc. Clelland. 1997. Human Resource Management. Prenhallindo. Jakarta
- [28.] Deci, E. L., and Ryan, R. M. 2001. "The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior." *Psychological Inquiry*, 11: 227-268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- [29.] Deci, E. L., and Ryan, R. M. 1987. "The support of autonomy and the control of behavior." *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 53: 1024-1037. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0022-3514.53.6.1024>
- [30.] Deci, E. L., Connell, J. P., and Ryan, R. M. 1989. "Self-determination in a work organization." *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74: 580-590. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0021-9010.74.4.580>
- [31.] Deeba, F., Usmani, R. A., Akhtar, M., Zahra, T., and Rasool, H. 2015. "Job satisfaction: Among doctors working in public and private tertiary care hospitals of Lahore." *The professional medical journal*, 22(10): 1373-1378.
- [32.] Dilig-Ruiz, A., MacDonald, I., Varin, M. D., Vandyk, A., Graham, I. D., and Squires, J. E. 2018. "Job satisfaction among critical care nurses: A systematic review." *International journal of nursing studies*, 88: 123-134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2018.08.014>
- [33.] Duffy, R. D., Autin, K. L., and Bott, E. M. 2015. "Work volition and job satisfaction: Examining the role of work meaning and person-environment fit." *The Career Development Quarterly*, 63: 126-140. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cdq.12009>
- [34.] Edwards, J. R. 1991. "Person-job fit: A conceptual integration, literature review, and methodological critique." *International Review of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 6: 283-357.
- [35.] Fernandez, S., and Moldogaziev, T. 2015. "Employee empowerment and job satisfaction in the US Federal Bureaucracy: A self-determination theory perspective." *The American review of public administration*, 45(4): 375-401. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0275074013507478>
- [36.] Fogg, Milton. 2004. "The Greatest Networker in the World." Three Rivers Press, New York.
- [37.] Fouché, E., Rothmann, S. S., and Van der Vyver, C. 2017. "Antecedents and outcomes of meaningful work among school teachers." *SA Journal of Industrial Psychology*, 43(1): 1-10. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajip.v43i0.1398>
- [38.] Fox, A. 1980. "The meaning of work." In Esland, G., and Salaman, G. (Eds.). *The Politics of Work and Occupations*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press.
- [39.] Fried, Y., and Ferris, G. R. 1987. "The validity of the job characteristics model: A review and meta-analysis." *Personnel Psychology*, 40: 287-322. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-6570.1987.tb00605.x>
- [40.] Gagne, M., and Deci, E. L. 2005. "Self-determination theory and work motivation." *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26: 331-362. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.322>
- [41.] Gecas, V. 1989. "The social psychology of self-efficacy." In W. R. Scott & S. Blake (Eds.), *Annual review of sociology*, 15: 291-316. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.so.15.080189.001451>
- [42.] Gist, M. 1987. "Self-efficacy: Implications for organizational behavior and human resource management." *Academy of Management Review*, 12: 472-485. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1987.4306562>
- [43.] Greguras, G. J., and Diefendorff, J. M. 2009. "Different fits satisfy different needs: linking person-environment fit to employee commitment and performance using self-determination theory." *Journal of applied psychology*, 94(2): 465. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0014068>
- [44.] Griffin, R. W. 1981. "A longitudinal investigation of task characteristics relationships." *Academy of Management Journal*, 24(1): 99-113. <https://doi.org/10.5465/255826>
- [45.] Hackman, and Oldham, G. R. 1981. *Work redesign*. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- [46.] Hackman, J. R., and Oldham, G. R. 1976. "Motivation through the design of work: Test of a theory." *Organizational behavior and human performance*, 16(2): 250-279. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073\(76\)90016-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-5073(76)90016-7)
- [47.] Ho, L.S. 2011. "Human spirituality and happiness: A tribute to life the source of inspirations, the source of hope, the source of joy." 11th edition, United State of America, Author House, 168p.
- [48.] Hoffman, B. J., and Woehr, D. J. 2006. "A quantitative review of the relationship between person-organization fit and behavioral outcomes." *Journal of vocational behavior*, 68(3): 389-399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2005.08.003>
- [49.] Hooper, P., Jutai, J. W., Strong, G., and Russell-Minda, E. 2008. "Age-related macular degeneration and low-vision rehabilitation: a systematic review." *Canadian Journal of Ophthalmology*, 43(2): 180-187. <https://doi.org/10.3129/i08-001>
- [50.] Huang, Y.H., Robertson, M.M., and Chang, K.I. 2004. "The role of environmental control on environmental satisfaction, communication, and psychological stress effects of office ergonomics

- training.” *Environment and Behavior*, 36: 617 – 637. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013916503262543>
- [51.] Illahi, W., and Cardall, M. 2018. “Therapeutic contact lens fitting in a large tertiary referral centre.” *Contact Lens and Anterior Eye*, 41(6): 471-472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clae.2018.10.019>
- [52.] Illardi, B. C., Leone, D., Kasser, T., and Ryan, R. M. 1993. “Employee and supervisor ratings of motivation: Main effects and discrepancies associated with job satisfaction and adjustment in a factory setting.” *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 23: 1789-1805. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1559-1816.1993.tb01066.x>
- [53.] Janik, M., and Rothmann, S. 2015. “Meaningful work and secondary school teachers' intention to leave.” *South African Journal of Education*, 35(2): 01-13. <https://doi.org/10.15700/saje.v35n2a1008>
- [54.] Jawad, M., Tabassum, T. M., Raja, S., and Abraiz, A. 2013. “Study on work place behaviour: role of person-organization fit, person-job fit & empowerment, evidence from Pakistan.” *Journal of Business and Management Sciences*, 1(4): 47-54.
- [55.] Judge, T. A., Locke, E. A., and Durham, C. C. 1997. “The dispositional causes of job satisfaction: A core evaluations approach.” *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 19: 151-188.
- [56.] Karakas, F. 2010. “Spirituality and performance in organizations: a literature review.” *Journal of Business Ethics*, 94(1): 89–106. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-009-0251-5>
- [57.] Karia, N., and Asaari, M. H. A. H. 2006. “The effects of total quality management practices on employees' work-related attitudes.” *The TQM magazine*.
- [58.] Kristof-Brown, A. L., Zimmerman, R. D., and Johnson, E. C. 2005. “Consequences of individual's fit at work: A meta-analysis of person-job, person-organization, person- group, and person-supervisor fit.” *Personnel Psychology*, 58: 281-342.
- [59.] Kumar, R., Ahmed, J., Shaikh, B. T., Hafeez, R., and Hafeez, A. 2013. “Job satisfaction among public health professionals working in public sector: a cross sectional study from Pakistan.” *Human resources for health*, 11(1): 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1478-4491-11-2>.
- [60.] Lee, Y.S., and Brand, J.L. 2005. “Effects of control over office workspace on perceptions of the work environment and work outcomes.” *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 25: 323–333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2005.08.001>
- [61.] Lee, Y.S., and Brand, J.L. 2010. “Can personal control over the physical environment ease distractions in office workplaces?” *Ergonomics*, 53: 324–335. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00140130903389019>
- [62.] Lotunani, et al., 2014. “The Effect of Competence on Commitment, Performance, and Satisfaction with Reward as a Moderating Variable (A Study on Designing Work plans in Kendari City Government, Southeast Sulawesi).” *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 3(2): 18-25.
- [63.] Marinucci, F., Majigo, M., Wattleworth, M., Paterniti, A. D., Hossain, M. B., & Redfield, R. 2013. “Factors affecting job satisfaction and retention of medical laboratory professionals in seven countries of Sub-Saharan Africa.” *Human resources for health*, 11(1): 1-7. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1478-4491-11-38>
- [64.] Mathew, J. E. 1991. “A cross level non recursive model of the antecedents of organisational commitment and satisfaction”. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(5): 607–661. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0021-9010.76.5.607>
- [65.] Mccoy, J.M., & Evans, G.W. 2005. “Physical work environment. In J. Barling, E.K. Kelloway, & M.R. Frone (Eds.), *Handbook of work stress*, 219–245.
- [66.] Naman, J.L. and Slevin, D.P. 1993 ‘Entrepreneurship and the concept of fit: a model and empirical tests’, *Strategic Management Journal*, 14(2): .137–153. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250140205>
- [67.] O’Reilly, C.A., Chatman, J. and Caldwell, D.F. 1991. “People and organizational culture: a profile comparison approach to assessing person-organization fit.” *Academy of Management Journal*, 34(3): 487–516. <https://doi.org/10.5465/256404>
- [68.] Ozer, E. M.. and Bandura, A. 1990. “Mechanisms governing empowerment effects: A self-efficacy analysis.” *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 58: 472-486. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0022-3514.58.3.472>
- [69.] Palmer, J. J., Chinanayi, F., Gilbert, A., Pillay, D., Fox, S., Jaggernath, J., and Blanchet, K. 2014. “Trends and implications for achieving VISION 2020 human resources for eye health targets in 16 countries of sub-Saharan Africa by the year 2020.” *Human resources for health*, 12(1): 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1478-4491-12-45>
- [70.] Parker, S.L., Jimmieson, N.L., and Amiot, C.E. 2013. “Selfdetermination, control, and reactions to changes in workload: A work simulation.” *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 18, 173. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0031803>
- [71.] Pham, H., and Kim, S.-Y. 2019. “The effects of sustainable practices and managers' leadership competencies on sustainability performance of construction firms.” *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 20, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2019.05.003>
- [72.] Piasentin, K. A., and Chapman, D. S. 2006. “Subjective person–organization fit: Bridging the gap between conceptualization and measurement.” *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 69(2): 202-221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2006.05.001>

- [73.] Pillay, R. 2009. "Work satisfaction of professional nurses in South Africa: a comparative analysis of the public and private sectors." *Human resources for Health*, 7(1): 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1478-4491-7-15>
- [74.] Ramson, P., Govender, P., and Naidoo, K. 2016. "Recruitment and retention strategies for public sector optometrists in KwaZulu-Natal Province, South Africa." *African Vision and Eye Health*, 75(1): 1-10. <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC196063>
- [75.] Ransetalu, A., et al. 2016. "The Effect of Competence, Motivation and Organisational Culture on Employee Performance: The Mediating Role of Organisational Commitment." *Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 4(9): 08-14. <https://doi.org/10.31227/osf.io/m7wqs>
- [76.] Renyut, B. C., Modding, H. B., and Bima, J. 2017. "The effect of organizational commitment, competence on Job satisfaction and employees performance in Maluku Governor's Office." <https://doi.org/10.31227/osf.io/hnwdt>
- [77.] Robbins, Stephen, P. 2007. "Organizational Behavior." Cliffs Prentice Hall, New Jersey
- [78.] Rosso, B. D., Dekas, K. H., and Wrzesniewski, A. 2010. "On the meaning of work: A theoretical integration and review." *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 30: 91-127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.riob.2010.09.001>
- [79.] Ryan, R. M., and Deci, E. L. 2000. "Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being." *American Psychologist*, 55: 68-78. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.68>
- [80.] Salam, A. 2016. "Job stress and job satisfaction among health care professionals." In Qatar Foundation Annual Research Conference Proceedings Volume 2016 Issue 1 p. HBOP2571. Hamad bin Khalifa University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5339/qfarc.2016.HBOP2571>
- [81.] Setyaningdyah, E., Nimran, K. U., and Thoyib, A. 2013. "The effects of human resource competence, organisational commitment and transactional leadership on work discipline, job satisfaction and employee's performance". *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 5(4): 140-153.
- [82.] Smith, B. 1997. "Empowerment - the challenge is now." *Empowerment in Organizations* 5(3): 120-122. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14634449710180008>
- [83.] Spector, P. E. 1986. "Perceived control by employees: A meta-analysis of studies concerning autonomy and participation at work." *Human Relations*, 11, 1005-1016.
- [84.] Spector, P. E. 1997. "Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences" (Vol. 3). Sage
- [85.] Spreitzer, G. M. 1995. "Psychological empowerment in the workplace: Dimensions, measurement, and validation." *Academy of Management Journal*, 38(5): 1442-1465. <https://doi.org/10.5465/256865>
- [86.] Spreitzer, G. M., Kizilos, M. A., and Nason, S. W. 1997. "A dimensional analysis of the relationship between psychological empowerment and effectiveness satisfaction, and strain." *Journal of management*, 23(5): 679-704. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014920639702300504>
- [87.] Steger, M.F., Dik, B.J., and Duffy, R.D. 2012. "Measuring meaningful work: The Work as Meaning Inventory (WAMI)." *Journal of Career Assessment*, 20: 322-337. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1069072711436160>
- [88.] Subari, S., and Riady, H. 2015. "Influence of training, competence and motivation on employee performance, moderated by internal communications." *American Journal of Business and Management*, 4(3): 133-145. <https://doi.org/10.11634/216796061706678>
- [89.] Syahrums, A., Brahmasari, I. A., and Nugroho, R. 2016. "Effect of competence, organizational culture and climate of organization to the organizational commitment, job satisfaction and the performance of employees in the scope of Makassar City government." *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 5(4): 52-64.
- [90.] Tasneem, S., Cagatan, A. S., Avci, M. Z., and Basustaoglu, A. C. 2018. "Job satisfaction of health service providers working in a public tertiary care hospital of Pakistan." *The Open Public Health Journal*, 11(1). <http://dx.doi.org/10.2174/1874944501811010017>
- [91.] Thomas, K. W., and Tymon, W. G. 1994. "Does empowerment always work: Understanding the role of intrinsic motivation and personal interpretation." *Journal of management Systems*, 6(2): 1-13.
- [92.] Thomas, K. W., and Velthouse, B. A. 1990. "Cognitive elements of empowerment." *Academy of Management Review*, 15: 666-681. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1990.4310926>
- [93.] Travaglianti, F., Babic, A., Pepermans, R., and Hansez, I. 2017. "Needs-supplies fit and behavioral outcomes: the mediating role of organizational identification." *Journal of Management & Organization*, 23(5): 709-727.
- [94.] Van Wingerden, J., Berger, L., and Poell, R. 2018. "The role of person-organization value fit in employees' experience of meaningful work, use of strengths and work engagement." *Business Management and Strategy*, 9(2): 1-17.
- [95.] Vansteenkiste, M., Neyrinck, B., Niemiec, C. P., Soenens, B., De Witte, H., and Van Den Broeck, A. 2007. "On the relations among work value orientations, psychological need satisfaction and

- job outcomes: A self-determination theory approach.” *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 80: 251-277.
<https://doi.org/10.1348/096317906X111024>
- [96.] Verquer, M. L., Beehr, T. A., and Wagner, S. H. 2003. “A meta-analysis of relations between person–organization fit and work attitudes”. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 63: 473-489.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0001-8791\(02\)00036-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0001-8791(02)00036-2)
- [97.] Warr, P. B., and Inceoglu, I. 2012. “Job engagement, job satisfaction, and contrasting associations with person-job fit.” *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 17: 129-138.
<https://psycnet.apa.org/doi/10.1037/a0026859>
- [98.] Wrzesniewski, A., Mccauley, C.R., Rozin, P. and Schwartz, B. 1997. “Jobs, careers and callings: People's relations to their work.” *Journal of Research in Personality*, 31: 21-33.
<https://doi.org/10.1006/jrpe.1997.2162>
- [99.] Zhang, M., Yang, R., Wang, W., Gillespie, J., Clarke, S., and Yan, F. 2016. “Job satisfaction of urban community health workers after the 2009 healthcare reform in China: a systematic review.” *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 28(1): 14-21.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzv111>
- [100.] Zontek, T. L., DuVernois, C. C., and Ogle, B. R. 2009. “Job satisfaction and issues related to the retention of environmental health professionals in North Carolina.” *Journal of Environmental Health*, 72(3): 10-15.

APPENDICES

Table 1: Socio-Demographic characteristics of participants:

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	53	35.3%
	Female	97	64.7%
Marital status	Single	106	70.0%
	Married	44	30.0%
Qualification	Bachelors	126	84.0%
	MS/M.Phil	24	16.0%
	Phd	0	0%
Experience	< 2 years	85	56.7%
	2-5 years	41	27.3%
	5-10 years	13	8.7%
	10 years	11	7.3%
Organization	Govt	8	5.3%
	Private	86	57.3%
	NGOs/ Trust	45	30.0%
	Academics	4	2.7%
	Optical	7	4.7%
Pay Package	>30k	54	36.0%
	30-60k	68	45.3%
	>60k	28	18.7%
1st Job Appointment	Yes	105	70.0%
	No	45	30.0%
Would you choose another career if given a choice?	Yes	47	31.3%
	No	54	36.0%
	Maybe	49	32.7%
Reason for choosing optometry	Only study opportunity	20	13.3%
	Very interested	81	54.0%
	Good income	7	4.7%
	Didn't know else	24	16.0%
	Others	18	12.0%

Table 2: Correlation analysis:

	1	2	3	4	5	6
1.Meaning	1					
2.Competence	0.481**	1				
3.Self-Determination	0.420**	0.579**	1			
4.Impact	0.296**	0.474**	0.601**	1		
5.P-O fit	0.330**	0.423**	0.485**	0.605**	1	
6.Job Satisfaction	-0.313**	-0.322*	-0.362**	-0.570**	-0.733**	1

*p< 0.05

**p<0.01

Table 3: Moderated regression analysis

Predictors	Job Satisfaction		
	B	R ²	ΔR ²
Step 1			
Control variable		0.216**	
Step 2			
Meaningful work	- 0.159		
Competence	0.095		
Self-determination	0.102		
Impact over work	-0.163*		
P-O Fit	-0.620**	0.599**	0.383**

Step 3			
MW * P-O Fit	0.109		
C * P-O Fit	0.017		
SD * P-O Fit	-0.027		
IOW * P-OO Fit	-0.035		
		0.606	0.007

Control Variables: Pay package, change career, n=150 *p< 0.05
 **p<0.01